

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Studies On Formulation of Herbal Toothpaste from Pongamia Seeds and Its Medicinal Evaluation

Dr. Raja Kumar Parabathina*, Krishna Varma, Guru Nikam

Institute of Biosciences and Technology, MGM University, Chhatrapati Sambhajinagar-431003.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 08 Dec. 2024

Keywords:

pH, Spreadability,
Foamability, Herbal
toothpaste, Antibacterial,
Antiinflammation.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.14311293

ABSTRACT

In day-to-day life and generation, the herbal products related to health are more acceptable than the synthetic products available in market which contain harmful chemicals which can cause major side effects to our body, where the natural ingredients-based product cannot cause such major side effects and are high in efficiency. In this formulation of toothpaste which contain the extract of Pongamia pinnata, clove oil, ginger oil, peppermint oil, and neem oil which have the antibacterial, inflammatory, and anti-cancer properties, wound healing. In this study the comparative study was carried out with the herbal toothpaste available in market in purpose to get and specialized data about the formulated toothpaste on the bases of important physical parameters such as PH, Spreadability, homogeneity, stability, foamability and antimicrobial properties, to make successful and more effective formulation. The aim of this study is formulated the herbal toothpaste with comparison and evaluation with other herbal toothpaste available in market. This study shows that our formulated herbal Toothpaste compare to available herbal toothpaste present in market is good more effective in term of physical parameters and contains natural ingredients, which is determined with the help of successful tests and results carried out.

INTRODUCTION

The 'Pongam Tree' also known as "Pongamia Pinnata" one of the India's richest and brightest trees on the bases of its medicinal properties. Pongamia' is a common name of the plant "Pongamia pinata" which comes from Tamil word 'pinnata' which means 'Pinnate leaves.' This tree is also known as 'Ponga,' 'Dalkaramacha,'

'Pongam,' and 'Punku' in Tamil. People called it 'Karanj', in Marathi, or 'Kanji' in both Hindi and Bengali. The Pongamia tree is affiliated to the family Leguminosae and 'Papilionaceae' is its subfamily. P. pinnata is a native plant to Australia and Asia. The Pongamia tree holds a long history in from today "Bharat and China "holds a long

***Corresponding Author:** Dr. Raja Kumar Parabathina*

Address: Institute of Biosciences and Technology, MGM University, Chhatrapati Sambhajinagar-431003.

Email ✉: rajakumar.parabathina@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

back record from, of use which has prompted scientists to investigate its pharmacological properties and justify its use as a treatment. This plant seeds have antioxidant, antiparasitic, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, properties. (Jelani et al.,2023). The Pongamia tree constituents are used broadly in traditional medicinal practice in India for a long time. The Pongamia seeds contains various phytochemical constituents belongs to alkaloids, glycosides, flavonoids, fixed oils, and carbohydrates. The constituents of seeds are non-toxic to the mammalian cells because the constituents have an ability to dissolve in body and can be used in the organic herbal tooth paste provide deep freshness and help to cleanse and oil present in the seeds provide strength and shining and have common solution to bad breath. Teeth is a one of the most tough parts and complex anatomical structure as well as histological structure in the body. teeth are the indispensable part of our digestive system, as such they help to break down the complex food material to small particles, by the action of masticate thus making it easy of digestion and ready to make and easy absorption of nutrients from food as it is necessary to maintain dental health and oral health. The oral health is important part of our overall health as teeth holds major part in the digestion so we should practice to clean our oral cavity and mouth to prevent from dental diseases and disorders. To prevent from emerging oral disease or disorder we should clean and maintain our oral hygiene to keep our mouth free of unwanted bacteria which grows due to food depositions between the teeth's and can lead to the major problem to our gums and teeth and also to prevent the most common problem among us bad breath. The most common immersing dental disorders are the toothache, tooth decay (cavities, dental caries) and gum diseases such as gingivitis and periodontists. Regular cleaning of teeth in day to day can help us to removal of dental plaque and

tartar which can prevent us from such dental disorders and gum diseases. To maintain the oral hygiene there are several products and formulation are available in market with purpose of cleaning the oral cavity and to avoid the bad breath and maintain freshness in mouth as they are toothpowder, mouth wash, breath fresher's, toothpaste. Tooth paste work as dosage to maintain our oral health and which act as the best defensive agent to our oral cavity which prevent us from diseases and oral disorder. tooth paste is not solid and liquid in nature they are semi-solid in nature and present as the paste or gel or emulsion form (Janvi et al.2024), they are basic formulation available in markets from today's modern world to the ancient time back to the 300-500B Bharat and China. Modern tooth paste formulation started to evolve from the ninetieth century (Shahidullah et al.2023). Toothpaste work as abrasive which cleans the dental plaque, tartar, and meal debris and free-living fluorides assist to clean the tooth. The herbal tooth paste can be the great choice rather than the artificial toothpaste containing extensive chemical which can harm the overall health the herbal tooth paste contains the natural constituent's which help to strengthen the teeth and shine and can be easily absorb by our body than the chemical toothpaste or synthetic toothpaste. As the herbal tooth paste formulation are very effective which contain lively chemical with polyphenols gums alkaloids glycosides etc. These formulations have additionally been established to have exclusive organic activities (Shahidullah et al .2023). Artificial toothpaste which has been formulated contain the different chemical components can harms the touchy a part of enamel like enamel, crown, dentin, roots of enamel and blood supplying nerves of enamel. Ideal properties of HERBAL TOOTHPASTE are: (Janvi et al.2024)

1. Provide good abrasive effect.
2. Should be non-toxic and non-irritant

3. Should not leave any stain in tooth
4. Keep the mouth fresh and clean
5. Provide prolonged action
6. Should cost effective
7. Should not hurt tissue
8. It should give pleasant aroma
9. It should taste good

Benefits of HERBAL TOOTHPASTE: (Janvi et al. 2024)

Herbal toothpastes have many beneficial effects for oral care, few of which are-

1. Herbal toothpaste is found to be useful to prevent against tooth decay.
2. Provides protection against cavity and plaque as well.
3. The herbal toothpaste act as whitening and strengthening effects to the teeth.
4. Helps in reduction of bleeding gums and inflammation.
5. The natural freshener used in herbal toothpaste helps in removing the bad Oduor and keeps mouth fresh.
6. Herbal toothpastes are safe for use as there is no artificial, synthetic, Chemical sweeteners, Flavors, colors or fragrances used in their preparation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Collection of Samples

Collection of Pongamia Seed from the southern Part of India through the local contact and were courier in polythene bag and transferred in sterile condition for the laboratory analysis in institute.

Preparation of seed sample.:

The Pongamia seed were further collected and shade dried in normal environmental conditions for 10-15 days, in this period of shade drying the observations were carried out for intervals of time of 1-2 days whether the samples got contaminated due to environmental conditions. These seeds were dried till there seed coat appearance was brown in color.

Oil Extraction from seed sample.:

The seed samples were collected and grinded from complex seed material to fine powder and used for oil extraction with the help of Soxhlet apparatus. The solvents used in the process were n-hexene, Methanol, and water in the ratio of 40:50:10 (in ml). The total amount of 1001ml solvent was used., The 30gms of sample was used for the oil extraction process and about 14-15 cycles of Soxhlet were carried out. This process was repeated about 2-3 times with same amount of sample, solvents composition and same range of cycles for each time. The extracted amount of oil was about 20ml after the soxhlation process.

Evaporation of Solvents.:

The oil was separated from solvents with the help of separating funnel and further the pure form of oil was obtained with help of simple evaporation techniques was performed where., The extracted oil was heated to the boiling point of solvents in range of 70-80 °C on hot plate and water bath. This evaporation process was performed for 2-3 times till 100% of solvent was not evaporated. After evaporation of solvents from oil the pure form of oil was extracted. Two simple tests were performed to identify the presence of oil and whether the 100% solvent.

Solubility test, and Translucent spot test.

Solubility test.:

The fats are soluble in organic solvents but are insoluble in water, so the 2-3 drops of sample were dissolved in test tube containing distil water and the test tube was Shaked for 2-3 times where the layer oil was observed at the upper surface of distil water which conform the presence of oil in sample and the bottom of test tube the water was crystal clear which conform the 100% solvent was evaporated from sample.

Translucent spot test.:

In this test the sample was rubbed between the folds of filter paper. The appearance of translucent spot was observed which confirms. The presence of oil in given sample.

Saponification.:

The equal amount of oil and sodium hydroxide was taken (1:1 w/V) and gently mixed while heating them together., where it will form a semi-solid product which is formed due to the lipid binding with the sodium hydroxide which is alkali in nature. Where this will help to dissolve the lipids present in oil in water. This semi solid nature product is further dried to solidify in room temperature. The solid product was weighed 1gm and equal amount of it was diluted in ten different test tubes which holds the amount of distil water from 1ml to 10ml and the all ten test tubes were vigorously Shaked, and incubated for 1-2 days in room temperature and observation was carried out whether the dilution got contaminated or any kind of bacterial or Fungal turbidity was grown or not, here there was no contamination and turbidity was observed the dilution were transparent and crystal clear. Further the highest dilution of 8ml, 9ml and 10ml were used to carry out the formulation of toothpaste with addition of natural oils which act as natural preservative and anti-inflammatory agents, cleaning, anti-bacterial agents.

Formulation of toothpaste.:

The highest dilution was selected and mixed with clove oil, ginger oil, mint oil and neem oil, with the help of following concentration shown in **Table 1.1** and with 1gm of plant-based gelatin powder.

There are two types of method are used to prepare for formulation of toothpaste.,

In this study the wet gum method is used to formulate the toothpaste.

•Dry gum method.

•Wet gum method.

Wet Gum method.:

All the liquid ingredients, such as oils and distil water were added to obtain a liquid phase Then the methyl paraben was added to obtained liquid phase with the water.

All the constituents such as calcium carbonate, sodium fluoride, sodium CMC, sodium benzoate sodium saccharine were simultaneously obtained to liquid phase and added to the formulation in very trace amount. As such all oil were simultaneously added to the medium as per the given concentration in Table 1.1.

Table1.1: Concentration of All Natural Constituents used in Formulation of Herbel Toothpaste.

Concentration of oil in ml	Pongamia Seed oil in "gm".	Clove oil of 0.5ml concentration in gm	Peppermint Oil concentration of 0.5ml	Ginger oil Concentration of 0.5ml	Neem oil Concentration Of 0.5ml
1ml	0.925gm	0.52 gm	0.449 gm	0.435 gm	0.466 gm
1.5ml	1.387gm	0.52 gm	0.449 gm	0.435 gm	0.466 gm
2ml	1.850gm	0.52 gm	0.449 gm	0.435 gm	0.466 gm
2.5ml	2.312gm	0.52 gm	0.449 gm	0.435 gm	0.466 gm
3ml	2.775gm	0.52 gm	0.449 gm	gm	gm

Manufacturing Process.:

Hot liquid Phase technique.:

In this technique, all the preservatives, binders, and abrasives are separately mixed. together to obtain dry powder of these ingredients in dry mixer. Then, in separate bowl water, sweeteners and humectants are mixed together to obtain liquid phase and then it is heated. After heating, hot

liquid phase is slowly added to the dry mixture/powder with a uniform stirring.

Then, under vacuum the obtained mass is mixed for 30 minutes. At last, under the vacuum surfactant and flavoring agent are added to the mixture and itis mixed again for the 5 minutes.

By using this technique, clear and homogenous toothpaste can formulate.

Evaluation and comparison of herbal toothpaste.:

Physical Examination (color, odour, Taste, Smoothness, relative density).:

Formulated toothpaste was evaluated for its color visually color was checked. Odour was founded by smelling the product. Taste was checked manually by tasting the product. The smoothness was tested by rubbing the product by fingers on palm.

pH:

The 1gm of the toothpaste from the container in was diluted in distil water to make aqueous suspension. Stir well to make a through suspension and determined the pH of suspension with 5min, using a pH meter.

Homogeneity.:

The toothpaste was placed in the falcon tubes during the incubation period and observation was made whether the toothpaste got any deterioration or get corrosive in the time or the toothpaste do extrude oil during the incubation period due to the inertness of tubes and gravity.

Determination of sharp and abrasive particles.:

The formulated toothpaste was on to the finger and scratched on the butter paper for 10-15cm long to check for presence of any sharp or abrasive particles.

Foamability.:

The foaming nature of toothpaste was checked and determined by taking 2 gm of toothpaste in 5ml of distil water in measuring cylinder initial volume was noted and then shaken 5-6 times. Final volume was noted.

Determination of moisture and volatile matter.:

Moisture and volatile matter were determined by using 2-5gm of toothpaste was placed in as Petri dish and dried in oven at 105 0 C which determine any volatile material is present in toothpaste or not. The Moisture was observed during the incubation period of toothpaste whether the toothpaste get dried or not.

Determination of Spreadability.:

For determination of Spreadability method slip and drag characteristics pf paste involve. The 1-2gm of formulated toothpaste was weighed and placed between two glass slide one over other and the beaker filled with full water was kept over the glass slides for 3mins. Measure the spreading (in cm) of the toothpaste after 3min.

Anti-Microbial Activity.:

The invitro anti-bacterial study of formulated toothpaste was performed by disc diffusion method by using Mueller Hinton agar against pathogenic bacteria strain, initially plates were streaked with inoculum and disc were made and diffused with formulated toothpaste and placed carefully on plates and zone of inhibition was recorded.

Shelf life of product.:

The formulated toothpaste was incubated for two months and the observation made about its nature, homogeneity, Odour, anti-fungal, antibacterial, any gassing or fermentation, phase separation or change in texture occurred or not. The incubation was carried out at room temperature kept in normal environmental conditions in surrounding.

Results

The seeds were grinded from complex material to the fine powder and further this powder was used to extract oil with the help of Soxhlet apparatus and soxhlation process where solvent is used to extract oil from seed sample was in volume about 20 ml and for confirmation the solubility test and translucent spot test was performed. As mentioned in Fig 1.

Fig 1: Extracted oil.

The determination of pH was carried out with the 1gm of toothpaste was gently mixed with 5ml of water in fresh beaker to make aqueous solution. The solution was prepared and the pH was determined in several intervals of time from the day when formulation of herbal toothpaste was carried out to the last day of product incubation in given period of two months, with help of pH Meter where the pH was measured in between 7 to 7.78 for all the concentration of toothpaste were formulated. As compared to herbal toothpaste available in market. As mentioned in **Fig-2**

Fig 2: Comparative analysis of pH.

To determine Foamability and the foaming power(Foamability) of herbal toothpaste., was determined by taking 2g of toothpaste with 5ml water in measuring cylinder initial volume was noted and then shaken. Final volume of foam was noted. According to **fig-3** mentioned below the formulated herbal toothpaste was non foaming in nature as compared to herbal toothpaste available in market was containing 4.5cm of foam.

Fig 3 - Comparative analysis of Foamability

The determination of the abrasive and sharp particles was carried out where the formulated herbal toothpaste was on to the finger and scratched on the butter Paper for 15-20cm long to check for the presence of any Sharp or abrasive particles. Repeated the same process for 2 -3 times no sharp or edge abrasive particles were found for all the concentration of formulated herbal toothpaste. For determination and Spreadability of Formulated herbal toothpaste and herbal toothpaste available in market. For the determination of Spreadability method the 1-2g of herbal Toothpaste was weighed and placed between two glass Slides (10 x 10cm) one over each other (sliding, shall no Take place), and the beaker filled with water was kept over them. To Measure the spreading (in cm) of toothpaste after 3 minutes. After Repeating the experiment, we observed that the formulated herbal toothpaste was spreading about 4.5cm and the Herbel toothpaste available in market was spreading about 3.5 cm as mentioned in **Fig-4**.

Fig 4 – Comparative study of Spreadability.

For determination of odour, texture and color. visually the color was checked and odour was found by smelling there was no change in color and odour the smell was aromatic and pleasant. There was no change in texture it was smoother and no symptoms of deterioration such as phase separation, gassing and fermentation from the day of formulation to the more than 30 days of incubation the paste consistency was same and the tools was stable in condition. To determine the anti-microbial Test- we performed the disc

diffusion method to check the anti-microbial properties of toothpaste against the bacteria *E. coli* where the formulated toothpaste resulted and shown the zone of inhibition about 1mm against the bacterial culture.

Fig 6.-Antimicrobial Test of formulated Herbal toothpaste

DISCUSSION:

In this study, we formulated the herbal toothpaste from Pongamia seed extract where the Pongamia seed oil was extracted with the help of Soxhlet process and further used to formulate the toothpaste with the help of different natural oils as mint oil which act as refreshing and soothing agent, clove oil which act as anti-inflammatory and natural cleaning agent, ginger oil for anti-inflammation and neem oil which act as antibacterial agent where this all oil act as natural preservative for toothpaste and as alternative for chemical preservatives which make our toothpaste herbal and natural as compared to market toothpaste. Where this toothpaste was foaming free compared to market toothpaste and can be best alternative present chemical and synthetic toothpaste available in market and was tested positive on all parameters tested and mentioned.

To determine the pH- The 1gm of toothpaste was gently mixed with 5ml of water in fresh beaker to make aqueous solution was prepared and the pH was determined in several intervals of time from formulation date, with help of pH Meter where the pH was maintained in between 7.78 to 8 for all concentration of formulated toothpaste. As compared to toothpaste available in market. To

Determine the abrasive and sharp particles- The contents on to the finger and scratched on the butter Paper for 15-20cm long to check for the presence of any Sharp or abrasive particles. Repeated the same process for 2 -3 times no sharp or edge abrasive particles were found. To determine the Foamability- The foaming power (Foamability) of herbal toothpaste was determined by taking 2g of toothpaste with 5ml water in measuring cylinder initial volume was noted and then shaken. Final volume of foam was noted. The formulated toothpaste was non foaming in nature as compared to herbal toothpaste available in market was containing 4.5cm of foam. Determination of Spreadability: we observed that the formulated toothpaste was spreaded about 4.5cm and herbal toothpaste available in market spreaded about 3.5cm. To determine the Homogeneity- The formulated toothpaste was stored in falcon tube after the formulation of toothpaste. After the storage of toothpaste, it was incubated for 30 days and onwards while the incubation period the observation was carried that there was no change in nature and condition of formulated toothpaste no oil was exoriated from paste and no corrosion and deterioration of toothpaste was observed. To determine the Odour, texture and colour – visually the colour was checked and odour was found by smelling there was no change in colour and odour the smell was aromatic and pleasant. There was no change in texture it was smoother and no symptoms of deuteriation such as phase separation, gassing and fermentation from the day of formulation to the more than 30 days of incubation the paste consistency was same and the tools was stable in condition. To determine the anti-microbial Test- The anti- microbial test was performed to check the anti-microbial properties of toothpaste against the bacteria *E. coli* where the formulated toothpaste resulted and shown the zone of inhibition about 1mm against the bacterial culture.

CONCLUSION

From the present investigation it is concluded that the formulated herbal toothpaste is non foaming and it is successfully obliged of all parameters of tooth paste which is available in market. The formulated toothpaste is shown 2 months of self-life and there is no change in texture as well as no symptoms of deterioration is observed. So that this study concludes that Pongamia seed oil tooth paste is optimum to use daily life as a regular tooth paste without any side effects.

(Curtesy: The authors used Dantkanti herbal toothpaste for comparative analysis in this study, as it is 100% herbal tooth paste available in market).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS:

We are thankful to Director, Institute of Biosciences and Technology, MGM University for support and guidance in this present research work and to provide the requirements regarding to our work. (Curtesy: The authors used Dantkanti herbal toothpaste for comparative analysis in this study, as it is 100% herbal tooth paste available in market).

Conflict Of Interest:

Authors declare no conflict of interest

REFERENCES

1. Ajum Trinawati., Suwarsono., Salikun. Herbal tooth paste extract (Betel Leaf, Lime and Salt) To Reduce Plaque. Journal center of Excellent: Health Assistive Technology. Vol (1) (2023), 2987-2200.
2. Durgesh Gautam*, Preetam Palkar, Kiran Maule, Shilpa Singh, Gopika Sawant, Chinmay Kuvalekar, Tushar Rukari, Dr. Vijay A. Jagtap. Preparation, Evaluation and comparison of Herbel toothpaste with marketed toothpaste. Asian Journal of Pharmacy and Technology. Vol 10(3) (2020).
3. Ishtiaq Jeelani¹, Tanzeela Qadir², Alisha Sheikh³, Mrinalini Bhosale⁴, Praveen Kumar Sharma², Andleeb Amin², Allah Nawaz¹, Aamir Sharif⁵, Abdul Hayee⁶, Muhammad Bilal⁷, Muhammad Rahil Aslam⁷ and Bilal Ahmed Mir¹. The Open Medicinal Chemistry Journal. Vol (1), (2023), 1874-1045.
4. M.S. Jadhav Janvi., Mr. Z. K. Khan. Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Toothpaste NCIM 3282. International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews vol (5) (2024), 7795-7701.
5. Nikita M. Rathi, Shital V. Sirsat, Sanket S. Toshniwal, Nikita T. Zagare, Shaikh Fazil Shaikh Mahamad. Formulation and Evaluation Study on Herbal Toothpaste: A Review. International journal of Noval Research and Development. Vol (7), (2022), 2456:4184.
6. B. Ruparani., Sheema Shahed., Ashritha ravali., M. Ramakanth. Effectiveness of An Herbal Toothpaste in Comparison with A Non-Herbal Tooth Paste in Patients with Gingivitis- A Randamized Control Trial International Journal dental and Medical Sciences Research. vol (3), (2021), 2582-6018.
7. S. M. Shahidullah., Somayeh Begum, Nishath Sultana., Sheema Samreen., Mohd Saleh. Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Toothpaste. International Journal of Research in Pharmaceutical and Nanoscience's. 12 (1), (2023), 32-37.
8. Sangram Keshari Panda, Aswini Sethi. Formulation and evaluation of a herbal toothpaste and compared with different marketed preparation, Inter Jour of Pha Res and App, 5(2), 2020, 557-560.
9. Senthilkumar K L, Venkateswaran S, Vasanthan A, Chiranjeevi P. Formulation development and evaluation of novel herbal toothpaste from natural source, International Journal of Pharmaceutical Chemistry and Analysis, 9(1), 2022, 17-21.
10. Somesh Anand Mali., Sameer Mafijoor Malik., Aakanksha Anil Mane., Prajakta Damodar Mane, Shivkumar Madhukar

Mangnale., Karan B Swami. Formulation And Evaluation of Herbal Toothpaste: Remedy for Oral Cancer. Vol (3), (2022),1380-1386.

11. Priyal G. 1, Maji Jose 2, Shruti Nayak 3, Vidya Pai 4, Surendra Prabhu, Evaluation of efficacy of different tooth paste formulations in reducing the oral microbial load - An in vivo

study, Biomedicine: 2021; 41(2)
Supplementary issues: 465-471.

HOW TO CITE: Dr. Raja Kumar Parabathina*, Krishna Varma, Guru Nikam, Studies On Formulation of Herbal Toothpaste from Pongamia Seeds and Its Medicinal Evaluation, Int. J. of Pharm. Sci., 2024, Vol 2, Issue 12, 842-850. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14311293>

